

EXAMINATION OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' LEVELS OF KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS REGARDING THE DEFINITION, SCOPE AND IMPORTANCE OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Abstract

This study aims to examine university students' awareness of the definition, scope and importance of cultural heritage and to make an original contribution to the field. For this purpose, the study was applied to undergraduate students registered at Uşak University Faculty of Education and Uşak University Faculty of Communication. In order to collect data in the study, a single focus group interview was conducted with 12 participants. In the study based on questions and answers, 9 questions were asked to the students for the purpose of the study. The participants of the research are university students aged between 18-29 who were selected by random sampling. According to the results of the study in which the maximum diversity proposition was applied; In general, it has been reached that university students have a high level of knowledge and awareness about the definition of cultural heritage, the elements it covers and its importance.

Keywords: Culture, Cultural Heritage, Awareness, Cultural Awareness.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of culture has emerged in socio-cultural life in the struggle of societies with the environment and in solving the problems arising from their common life together. It also refers to the living environments created and organized by people and their relations with each other. Culture gives societies its characteristic features, and because it can vary and can be applied in every society, it provides the transfer of customs, traditions and customs, value judgments and experiences from the past to all individuals in the society (Seyyar, 2003; Kim and., 2007). UNESCO; defines culture as a set of facts that define certain concrete and intangible values that define the identity of a community or society, lifestyles, customs and traditions, values and beliefs of societies (Oğuz, 2011: 77).

The concept of culture is in a constant relationship with the concept of heritage because they are the common product of humanity. Heritage includes artistic elements used in life, architectural works, cultural landscape values, as well as abstract traditions and customs, songs and folk songs, oral literature products, performances and rituals (Karaca, and., 2017: 56). It is defined as a set of all concrete and intangible values that are accepted by all segments of society and created and adopted by the people (Silverman & Rugless, 2007: 47). Cultural heritage, which is the synthesis of the concepts of culture and heritage, is the sum of all tangible and intangible values that contain the identity characteristics, accumulated experiences, and traces of life from the past (Halaç & Bademci, 2021: 17). With the “*Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage*” accepted by UNESCO in 1972, the concepts of natural and cultural heritage and tangible cultural heritage were accepted and entered the literature (UNESCO, 1972). The Ministry of Culture and Tourism in Turkey (2009) defines cultural heritage as “*All kinds of works that are inherited from the past and wanted to be left to the future for different reasons, that exist physically and that are made by people, and the set of values belonging to a society*”. It carries out studies in this field by giving importance to the transfer of information.

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It is possible to evaluate all the facts and data that have been accumulated and developed since the beginning of human history, enriched and transferred to the next generations within the scope of cultural heritage (Fidan, 2013: 31). Cultural heritage connects the past with the present and the future like a bridge, enabling interaction and communication between generations. The process of evaluating culture as a heritage is based on the transferability of all value judgments of a society to next generations (Kurtar & Somuncu, 2013: 44). People's communication, behavioral traces and ways of expressing themselves, which individuals and societies value, attach and protect a special meaning, are effective dimensions in the formation of cultural heritage (Çetin, 2010: 25). It gives a sense of belonging to individuals in the society in terms of a place, a nation and a culture, and it contains values that help individuals to resolve their identity confusions (Kiper, 2004: 89). Cultural heritage is also considered as a part of the common heritage in terms of reflecting the lifestyles of societies, all tangible and intangible products and their creative features (Yeşilbursa, 2013: 166). Cultural heritage elements of a society provide that society with many tangible and intangible data about their past. Recognition and protection of cultural heritage by the society enables that society to be aware of its historical past and at the same time to protect this data (Endresen, 1999: 231).

Cultural heritage values are also tangible and intangible values that have been formed as a result of the accumulation of many factors such as cultural, social, religious and economic. The cultural accumulation of the past and the sum of the basic elements that make up a society are accepted as cultural heritage. UNESCO, which has a universal perspective, cultural heritage; *“It is a general name given to the works created by previous generations that are believed to have universal values, language and culture, which have survived to the present day.”* defines as. In order for an item to be accepted as a cultural heritage value, this item must be owned by the society. Cultural property should be socioculturally accepted and adopted by the members of the society, protected and kept under surveillance, if it is an intangible cultural asset, it should be transferred to future generations and these values should be promoted.

In accordance with the 1972 Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, UNESCO evaluates cultural heritage in two main parts as *“Tangible Cultural Heritage”* and *“Intangible Cultural Heritage”*. According to the Convention for the Protection of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, intangible cultural heritage; means the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills and related tools, materials and cultural spaces that communities, groups and in some cases individuals define as part of their cultural heritage. This heritage, handed down from generation to generation, is constantly recreated by communities and groups based on their interaction with their environment, nature and history, giving them a sense of identity and continuity. Thus, it contributes to respect for cultural diversity and human creativity. Intangible Cultural Heritage is based on oral tradition. Therefore, it is a living and living heritage site. As with tangible cultural products, it is not only a unique and authentic heritage that needs to be protected, but also a reproduced heritage site. Thus, the *“Convention for the Protection of the Intangible Cultural Heritage”* was adopted on 17 October 1972. The Convention entered into force in our country by being published in the Official Gazette and Turkey became a party as of 27 March 2006.

1. Tangible And Intangible Cultural Heritage

Cultural heritage is divided into two parts: tangible cultural heritage and intangible cultural heritage (Müfettiş, 2009: 63). The tangible cultural heritage includes the observable

works of the cultures of the societies that represent civilizations; architectural structures, technical backgrounds, roads, bridges, etc. It consists of tangible features that include transportation networks. All kinds of tangible and tangible structures and artifacts and environmental standards created by societies are accepted as tangible cultural heritage elements (Dönmez, 2014: 98). At the beginning of the tangible values of cultural heritage are cultural landscape areas, archaeological sites, squares where important historical events take place, monumental structures and elements, while intangible cultural heritage is traditions and customs, customs, dance, music, performances and consists of values such as ritual (Gümüşçü, 2018: 36). UNESCO and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Turkey attach great importance to tangible cultural heritage elements and carry out many studies related to their protection and promotion.

In addition to tangible cultural heritage values, intangible cultural heritage values also have a great importance in cultural heritage. Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage adopted by UNESCO in 2003; It defines it as *“the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills and related tools, materials and cultural spaces that communities, groups and in some cases individuals define as part of their cultural heritage”*. Intangible cultural heritage is an accumulation that can be transferred from generation to generation, the environment of societies and human communities, the whole of values that can be renewed and shaped by the interaction of nature and historical data (Köroğlu, and.; 2018). The existence and continuation of social identity ensures the formation of interest and respect in the process of developing cultural diversity and creative elements. The concept of intangible cultural heritage, which is based on oral tradition, is a living, developing, updated and reproducible heritage area (Kuşçuoğlu, 2017: 53).

Intangible cultural heritage consists of moral characteristics such as customs, traditions, attitudes and behaviors that reflect the self-identity of a nation or society and guide it in determining its identity characteristics (Bilgiseven, 1995: 53). Intangible cultural heritage is defined as practices, representations, forms of oral expression, skills and knowledge and the materials associated with them, which are evaluated within the scope of cultural heritage by the society or individuals. Intangible cultural heritage is, in a sense, the common memory that is transferred from generation to generation in societies, and that enables new generations to live by being transferred (Uslu, 2006: 98). This cultural heritage is the cultural memory of the society that it has come from for generations and is wanted to be transferred to the next generation.

Cultural awareness means being aware of the cultural values of individuals (Mokrane, 2020: 17). While the lack of awareness of people about cultural heritage brings people out of the cultural heritage protection process, this situation causes cultural heritage to be damaged and destroyed (Shankar & Swamy, 2013: 46). In this context, the concept of awareness has an important place in the sustainability of cultural heritage values (Bademci, 2021: 98). It is necessary for the people who have cultural heritage and live in the vicinity to have awareness of cultural heritage values. When this awareness is not created, the sustainability of cultural heritage will not be fully successful (Köroğlu, and., 2018). In addition, awareness of cultural heritage creates individuals who take responsibility for the recognition and development of these values, not just the protection of this heritage. As a result of this awareness and awareness, cultural heritage can be preserved and transferred to future generations, and it is possible to deliver these values to large masses and to benefit from cultural tourism (Külcü, 2015: 67). Sustainability of cultural heritage; It is not possible to ignore the awareness of the society about these values and try to protect it only with legal and administrative rules. Cultural heritages are also of great economic importance for the area they are in (Özgen, 2016: 90). By raising

awareness of cultural heritage values and promoting them adequately, these cultural heritage sites will become a center of attraction for many domestic and foreign tourists. Cultural heritage awareness, education and promotion have an important place in terms of the sustainability of this heritage. As a result of these, in a loop system that feeds each other, the importance given to the cultural heritage values in the area will increase and the public will understand the importance of protection with this awareness.

2. Method

The sample of the study, which was carried out with the phenomenological analysis method, consists of undergraduate and graduate students registered at Uşak University Faculty of Education and Uşak University Faculty of Communication. The participants of the research are university students aged between 18-29 who were selected by random sampling. The research was applied to a single group of 12 people. Focus group interview was used as data collection method. In the application, a single session was held and the interview time in the session was planned as 40 minutes. Question guide developed by the researcher was used in the session. There was no recorder and reporter in the focus group interview; Written transcription, coding and content analysis of the data were carried out by the researcher. The data were recorded in writing by the participants. In the interviews based on questions and answers, 9 questions were asked and went from specific to general. Participants were allowed to sit in a U-shape and two pieces of paper and pens were placed on the tables for each participant. S. 1., S. 2., S. 3. etc. abbreviations refer to participating students. In this study, focus group interview was used as a data collection tool, and each of the questions asked to the participants was determined as a selected main theme. The sub-themes were created according to the answers given, and the data obtained were presented in tables, including the main theme, sub-theme and the number of students.

In this context; During the focus group discussion, the following questions were asked to the participants:

- ❖ **Question 1:** What do you think cultural heritage means?
- ❖ **Question 2:** What comes to mind when you think of cultural heritage?
- ❖ **Question 3:** What qualities do you think an asset should have in order to be a cultural heritage?
- ❖ **Question 4:** Does cultural heritage reflect the value of a city?
- ❖ **Question 5:** What do you think the ancient city and traditional rural architecture mean?
- ❖ **Question 6:** What do you think about the effect of traditional children's games on the transfer of culture?
- ❖ **Question 7:** What are the reasons for forgetting traditional children's games, what can be done to ensure that they are not forgotten and transferred from generation to generation?
- ❖ **Question 8:** Why do you think cultural heritage is important and why should we protect it?

3. Findings And Evaluation

Within the scope of the study, the questions asked to the participants and the tables of the answers received are given in tables together with the main themes and sub-themes obtained from the answers.

In order to determine the awareness of the students about the definition of cultural heritage, the students were asked the question *“What do you think is the definition of cultural heritage?”* question was posed. The answers to the question, the themes and the number of students are given in Table.:1.

THEMES	f
Cultural Heritage	10
<i>Historical Artifacts</i>	5
<i>Traditions and Customs</i>	3
<i>Ancient Life Culture</i>	2

Table.:1 *“What do you think is the Definition of Cultural Heritage?” Analysis of the Answers to the Question*

Based on the main theme of “Cultural Heritage”, sub-themes based on the students' views emerged as *“Historical artifacts, Traditions and customs, and Ancient life culture”*. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme of “historical artifacts” is 5. Expressing his opinion based on the sub-theme of "historical artifacts", S. 8.; He says, "Historical remains from our ancestors, from societies living in the past, to the present day". S. 3. is “The items used by ancient people and historical artifacts.”, S. 10. on the other hand; *“They are buildings and structures that have been built by people in the past, which have survived for many years.”* says. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Traditions and customs” is 3. One of the students, S. 4., who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of *“Traditions and customs, is the survival and continuation of our old traditions.”* says. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Life Culture of the Ancients” is 2. One of the students, S. 2., who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Life culture of the ancients”, *“It is the survival of the life cultures of the people in ancient times.”* says. If 2. 1.; *“It is information about how and what happened to the past life.”* says. 2 students did not make any statement on the subject.

In the second question, the students were asked, *“What comes to your mind when you say cultural heritage?”* question was posed. S. 2. defines cultural heritage as *“the items used by ancient people and historical artifacts”*. As an example, he stated *“Our folk songs, food cultures, folk dances”*. S. 7., on the other hand, gave the answer *“I don't know exactly”* and gave the answer *“It could be ancient coins, coins”* as an example. The answers to the posed question were analyzed and shown in Table 2.

THEMES	f
Cultural Heritage Sample	10
<i>Folkloric Cultural Values</i>	6

<i>Historical Buildings and Furnitere</i>	4
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Table.:2 “What Comes to Your Mind When You Say Cultural Heritage?” Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “Cultural Heritage Sample”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as **“Folkloric cultural values and Historical buildings and objects”**. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Folkloric Cultural Values” is 6. S. 4., expressing his opinion based on this theme, says *“he art of carving, wrought iron and embroidery”*. S. 8. is *“Food culture, folk dances”* and S. 10.; He says *“behavior, local dialect, way of speaking”*. The number of students who gave their opinions based on the sub-theme of “Historical buildings and objects” is 4. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 6. says *“Castles, ancient living spaces, pyramids”*. One of the remaining 2 students gave the answer *“I don't know”* and the other gave an irrelevant answer with the discourse of *“Making good food”*. In this direction, it can be said that students mostly show folkloric values and intangible cultural heritage as examples.

The third question was **“What qualities do you think an asset should have in order to be a cultural heritage?”** It was aimed to determine the awareness of the qualities of cultural heritage by asking the question.

THEMES	f
Cultural Heritage Attributes	10
<i>Historical and Sustainable Characteristics</i>	5
<i>Having a Documentary Quality from the Past</i>	3
<i>Carrying a Universal Quality</i>	2

Table.: 3 “What Qualities Do You Think A Property Should Have in order to be a Cultural Heritage?” Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “Cultural Heritage Qualities”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as **“Historical and sustainable quality, documentary quality of the past and universal quality”**. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Historical and sustainable quality” is 5. S. 1. one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, says, *“It should have a historical background and a deep-rooted history”*. S. 5. *“It has a historical past and its traces still continue and it is sustainable.”* and S. 9.; *“It has survived until today and its continuity,”* he says. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “having a documentary quality from the past” is 2. S. 1., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, *“It gives us information about the old life.”* says. If S. 8.; He says, *“It gives us information about ancient history and it can be transferred to people”*. The number of students who expressed an opinion

based on the sub-theme of “having a universal quality” is 1. S. 7., one of the students who expressed an opinion based on this theme, says *“It is a value that belongs to all, it is universal and it is considered important from a scientific point of view”*. 2 students did not give any answer to the question. In order for an asset to be considered as a cultural heritage value, it must have certain criteria. These criteria consist of various criteria such as documentary value, historical value, aesthetic and architectural value, economic and use value, scarcity and local value and integrity value.

In order to determine students' awareness of cultural heritage on the value of a city, **“Do you think cultural heritage reflects the value of a city?”** question was posed. The analysis of the answers to the question is shown in the table below.

THEMES	f
Cultural Heritage and Urban Value	10
<i>Yes Reflects</i>	8
<i>No Does Not Reflect</i>	2

Table.: 4 “Does Cultural Heritage Reflect the Value of a City?” Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “Cultural Heritage and Urban Value”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as **“Yes Reflects and No Does Not”**. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme “Yes Reflects” is 8. S. 11., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, said, *“I think it definitely reflects it. The more cultural richness it has, the more valuable it will be.”* If S. 4.; *“Yes. For example, Cappadocia is a very valuable place. Thanks to its cultural heritage”*. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme “No Does Not Reflect” is 2. One of the students, S. 1., who expressed an opinion based on this theme, said, *“If a city does not have much cultural heritage, it does not show that it is worthless. Maybe they don't know how to show and promote what's available”*. If S. 8.; *“I don't think so”* he says. 2 students stated that they do not know whether the cultural heritage reflects the value of a city or not.

In order to determine the awareness of the students about the ancient city and traditional rural architectural values that are within the scope of cultural heritage, **“What do you think the Ancient City and Traditional Rural Architecture Mean?”** question was posed.

THEMES	f
Ancient City	8
<i>Historical Settlements and Processes</i>	5

<i>Historical Artifacts and Ruins</i>	3
<i>Traditional Rural Architecture</i>	3
<i>Small Settlement Areas</i>	3

Table.: 5 “*What Do You Think Ancient City and Traditional Rural Architecture Mean?*”
Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “Ancient City”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as “***Historical Settlements and Processes and Historical Artifacts and Ruins***”. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Historical Settlements and Processes” is 5. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 8. says, “*The areas that hosted a very old settlement, for example, the Ancient City of Aizanoi*”. S. 1. is “*Formerly formed urban areas*” and S. 6. is; “*Places like the city of Aizanoi. They are cities dating back to very ancient times*”. The number of students who gave their opinions based on the sub-theme of “Historical Artifacts and Ruins” is 3. S. 2., one of the students who expressed an opinion based on this theme, says, “*The works of ancient kingdoms and civilizations are artifacts such as their tombs.*” S. 5. is “*Pyramids built by people in the past, caves are called places of shelter*” and S. 10. is; “*For example, Mesatimoles. “Historical remains of very old settlements,*” he says. One student did not express any opinion on the subject. Based on the main theme of “Traditional Rural Architecture”, the only sub-theme based on students' opinions, “Small residential areas”, emerged. The number of students who gave their opinion based on the sub-theme of “small residential areas” is 3. S. 7., one of the students who expressed an opinion based on this theme, says “*Smaller campuses compared to cities*”. If S. 4.; It says “*Smaller residential areas*”. Other students did not express any views on traditional rural architecture.

In order to determine their awareness of the role of traditional children's games in the transfer of cultural heritage, the students were asked “***What do you think about the effect of traditional children's games on the transfer of culture?***” question was posed.

THEMES	f
<i>Traditional Children’s Games</i>	11
<i>Games are a Living Cultural Heritage</i>	5
<i>Games are Tools for cultural Transfer</i>	4
<i>Tradition and Culture Are One</i>	2

Table.: 6 “*What Do You Think About The Effect of Traditional Children's Games on the Transfer of Culture? Analysis of the Answers to the Question*”

Based on the main theme of “Traditional Children's Games”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as “***Games are a living cultural heritage, Games are a tool for cultural transfer and Tradition and culture are a whole***”. The number of students who expressed an

opinion based on the sub-theme of “Games are a Living Cultural Heritage” is 5. S. 2., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, states that “*Traditional children's games are important elements of cultural heritage since they have been preserved from the past to the present*”. “*These games are games that even our grandparents played when they were kids. Therefore, they are the cultural heritage itself*”. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Games are Tools for Cultural Transfer” is 4. One of the students, S. 3., who expressed an opinion based on this theme, said, “There is a piece of the values of the society and culture in every children's play. Traditional games are also a tool that ensures the transfer of cultural heritage from the past to the present. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme “Tradition and Culture are a Whole” is 5. One of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, S. 10. said, “*While our traditions are shaped within our culture, they also shape the culture. In this context, traditional children's games should not be considered separately from cultural heritage*” says. 1 student said that he was undecided.

In order to determine the awareness of the students that traditional children's games can not protect their existence, “*What are the Reasons for Forgetting Traditional Children's Games, What Can Be Done to Not Be Forgotten and Transferred from Generation to Generation?*” question was posed.

THEMES	f
Reasons for Forgetten Traditional Children's Games	12
<i>Technological Tools</i>	7
<i>Shrinking Families</i>	2
<i>Not Appealing to the New Generation</i>	3
<i>What To Do</i>	9
<i>It Should Be Told In Schools</i>	4
<i>Festivals, Promotions</i>	3
<i>Joint Play Activities with Families</i>	2

Table.: 7 “*What are the Reasons for Forgetting Traditional Children's Plays, What Can Be Done to Not Be Forgotten and Transferred from Generation to Generation?*” Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “Reasons for Forgetting Traditional Children's Games”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as “*Technological tools, families getting smaller and not appealing to the new generation*”. The number of students who gave opinions based on the sub-theme of “Technological Tools” is 7. One of the students, S. 5., who commented on this theme, said, “*Children are now playing virtual games on tablets and*

phones. They seem more attractive.” On the other hand, S. 6. said, “I think the high rate of use of technology at all ages has caused traditional children's games to be forgotten.” The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Shrinking of Families” is 2. One of the students, S. 9., who expressed an opinion based on this theme, said, “In the past, grandfathers and grandmothers lived with or close to their grandchildren. They would teach them these games. Now families are mostly nuclear families. No one is teaching the children.” says. If S. 8.; “Now the parents are usually working and the children are either at school or in kindergarten. They do not live with their elders. Neither the parents nor the elders are interested in the children in this matter”. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme “Does not appeal to the new generation” is 3. S. 10., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, says, “Traditional children's games may not appeal to them because the interests of the new generation children, the environment they were born into and the opportunities offered are very different.” Based on the main theme of “What Should Be Done”, the sub-themes based on the students' opinions were determined as “Should be explained in schools, Festivals and promotions should be made, and Joint game activities with families”. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme “Should be Told in Schools” is 7.S. 7., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, said, “I think history, sociology, etc. The importance of these games should be explained to the students at every education level in the lessons”. If S. 3. He says, “It would be better if the teachers explained these to the students, and if these games were given to teacher candidates as a lesson in universities.” The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Festivals and Promotions Should Be Made” is 7. S. 5., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, said, “Municipalities or related institutions can organize traditional game festivals.” says. If S. 11.; “Traditional games can be promoted in writing, verbally or visually through the media. Its importance and its contents can be mentioned”. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Common Game Activities with Families” is 7. S. 3., one of the students who expressed their opinions based on this theme, said, “Works where families teach traditional games to children's groups can be organized. Thus, these games are transferred from family to child.” S. 8. said, “Let grandparents be invited to schools. Let them both tell and play these games. Thus, they both attract the attention of children and create awareness.” says. 3 students stated that they do not know what to do.

In order to determine the awareness of the students about the importance and protection of cultural heritage, the students were asked, “**Why do you think cultural heritage is important and why should we protect it?**” The question has been posed. Some students gave answers only about its importance or only about its protection.

THEMES	f
Importance of Cultural Heritage	10
Giving us Information About the Past	3
Having a Universal Value	1
Inherited Form Our Ancestors	3

Sustainability	2
Tourism	1

Table.: 8 “Why Do You Think Cultural Heritage is Important and Why Should We Protect It?” Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “The Importance of Cultural Heritage”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as **“It provides us with information about the past, It has a universal value, It is inherited from our ancestors, Sustainability and Tourism”**. The number of students who gave their opinions based on the sub-theme of “Giving Us Information about the Past” is 3. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 6. says, “It is important because it reflects the cultural characteristics of those who lived in the past.” S. 2. “We must preserve it because it is a historical document and can be passed on to future generations” and S. 3.; “It needs to be preserved in order to show and transfer past experiences and events to future generations. However, historical buildings and structures should be protected because they give information about the past. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme “Has a Universal Value” is 1. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 9. says, “We must protect the cultural heritage because it is accepted and valued by everyone.” The student who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Inheritance from Our Ancestors” is 3. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 4. says, “If it is inherited from our ancestors, it is important for us, so we must protect it and maintain it.” The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the “Sustainability” sub-theme was 2. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 6. said, “It should be preserved in order to pass it on to future generations.” says. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Tourism” is 1. Expressing his opinion based on this theme, S. 9. says, “It should be protected because it can be beneficial for tourism.” 2 students did not express any opinion on the subject.

In order to determine the level of awareness of the students for the promotion and protection of the cultural heritage values of the region they live in. **“What can be done to promote and protect the cultural heritage within the borders of the region you live in?”** question was posed.

THEMES	f
Promotion and Protection of Cultural Heritage	11
Local Events	6
Seminar and Conference in Schools	3
Publicity Through Media	2

Table.: 9 “What Can Be Done to Promote and Protect the Cultural Heritage within the Borders of the Region You Live in?” Analysis of the Answers to the Question

Based on the main theme of “Promotion and Protection of Cultural Heritage”, sub-themes based on students' opinions emerged as “**Local events, seminars and conferences in schools and promotion through the media**”. The number of students who expressed their opinions based on the sub-theme “Local Activities” is 6. One of the students, S. 4. who expressed an opinion based on this theme, said, “*Each region can promote its cultural heritage with festivals. It's like Eşme's kilim festival...*” If S. 9. “These values should be promoted in order to protect and protect the cultural heritage of the people. Promotion days can be held where the cultural heritage elements of the region and their importance are mentioned” The number of students who gave their opinions based on the sub-theme “Seminar and Conference in Schools” is 3. One of the students, S. 1. who expressed an opinion based on this theme, said, “*With seminars and conferences, the elements within the scope of cultural heritage, the cultural heritage values of the regions, what can be done to protect etc. I think it should be explained.*” says. If S. 8.; “*Teachers, academics, and even students in schools should work on these issues.*” says. The number of students who expressed an opinion based on the sub-theme of “Publication through the Media” is 2. One of the students, S. 7., who expressed an opinion based on this theme, said, “*Social media tools and technological devices can be used for this purpose. Public service announcements can be made.*” 1 student said, “*I don't know*”.

RESULT

The concept of awareness has an important place in the sustainability of cultural heritage values. It is necessary for the people who have cultural heritage and live in the vicinity to have awareness of cultural heritage values. When this awareness is not formed, the sustainability of cultural heritage will not be fully successful. In addition, awareness of cultural heritage creates individuals who take responsibility for the recognition and development of these values, not just the protection of this heritage. As a result of this awareness and awareness, cultural heritage can be preserved and transferred to future generations, and it is possible to deliver these values to large masses and to benefit from cultural tourism. Sustainability of cultural heritage; It is not possible to ignore the awareness of the society about these values and try to protect it only with legal and administrative rules. Cultural heritages are also of great economic importance for the area they are in. By raising awareness of cultural heritage values and promoting them adequately, these cultural heritage sites will become a center of attraction for many domestic and foreign tourists. Cultural heritage awareness, education and promotion have an important place in terms of the sustainability of this heritage. As a result of these, in a loop system that feeds each other, the importance given to the cultural heritage values in the area will increase and the public will understand the importance of protection with this awareness.

In order to be able to evaluate the existing cultural heritage and be determined to carry it to the next level, it is necessary to be aware of the cultural heritage, and it is necessary to inhale the cultural environment, that is, to experience it. In other words, internalizing the meanings of cultural heritage values is important for the sustainability of cultural heritage. As a result of the study, it was seen that the awareness levels of university students about the definition, scope and importance of cultural heritage were mostly high. More than 80% of the students generally gave answers to the questions asked related to the subject. Some abstained or stated that they did not know. Places, subjects, etc. within the scope of cultural heritage. It was seen that the level of knowledge of the students about the items was generally high. However, it can be said that they should be informed in more detail about these issues and they should be motivated to participate in studies. It has been observed that approximately 85% of the students have an idea about the promotion and protection of cultural heritage. Education

faculty students have come to the forefront about the relationship between traditional children's games and cultural heritage, and it has been observed that all students have knowledge and awareness on this subject in general.

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